

Perceptions, Expectations, and Engagement of PSU–Narra Students Toward the Attainment of Ambisyon Natin 2040

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Abstract

This study examined the perceptions, expectations, and engagement of Palawan State University–Narra Campus students toward the attainment of AmBisyon Natin 2040, the Philippine government’s long-term development vision. Grounded on the role of youth in national development, the study aimed to assess students’ awareness, outlook, and participation in initiatives aligned with the vision, as well as determine the relationship between their demographic profile and these variables. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 332 undergraduate students selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, and Pearson’s r correlation. Results showed that students generally have positive perceptions and awareness of AmBisyon Natin 2040, recognizing its relevance, clarity, and alignment with their personal goals. They demonstrated moderate expectations, expressing

optimism about improvements in quality of life, education, healthcare, and employment, while remaining cautious about full government implementation. Findings also revealed active student engagement in sustainable development activities, responsible citizenship, environmental conservation, and advocacy, indicating a willingness to contribute to nation-building. Correlation analysis revealed no significant relationship between students’ year level or program and their perceptions, expectations, and engagement, suggesting consistency across demographic groups. The study concludes that PSU–Narra students are aware, supportive, and engaged in the national development vision. However, increased information dissemination and stronger institutional support are necessary to enhance awareness and sustain participation. The findings emphasize the crucial role of higher education institutions in empowering youth as active partners in achieving AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Keywords: *Perceptions, Expectations, Engagement, Attainment of AmBisyon Natin 2040, National Development*

INTRODUCTION

National development is a long-term and continuous process that requires the participation of all sectors of society, especially the youth who represent the future of the nation. In the Philippines, the government has articulated a collective long-term vision known as AmBisyon Natin 2040, launched in 2016 under the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA). This vision captures the aspirations of

Filipinos for a “matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay”—a strongly rooted, comfortable, and secure life by the year 2040. It serves as a guide for policymaking, program development, and implementation across administrations (Reyes et al., 2019).

Filipinos are strongly rooted (*matatag*). Filipino families live together; there is work-life balance so that there is time to spend with family even for members who work. On weekends, families and friends enjoy time together in parks and recreational centers. It is a high-trust society with a strong sense of community. There are volunteer opportunities, and Filipinos spend time to serve the community, help others who are in need, and contribute to various causes (Lamberte, et al., 2019).

Filipinos are comfortable (*maginghawa*). No one is poor, no one is ever hungry. Filipino families live in comfortable homes with the desired amenities and secure tenure. Families and friends are within reach because transport is convenient and affordable, and they can take a vacation together within the country and abroad. Children receive quality education so that they realize their full potentials and become productive members of society. Decent jobs that bring sustainable income are available, including opportunities for entrepreneurship (Lamberte, et al., 2019).

Filipinos are secure (*panatag*). Filipinos feel secure over their entire lifetime. They expect to live long and enjoy a comfortable life upon retirement. There are resources to cover unexpected expenses, and there are savings. They feel safe in all places in the country. Filipinos trust their government because it is free of corruption and provides service to all its citizens equally (Lamberte, et al., 2019).

Aligned with the Commission on Higher Education's mandate and the global aspirations outlined in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, *AmBisyon Natin 2040*— *matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay*—and the vision of “*Bagong Pilipinas*,” Palawan State University-Narra Campus, along with other State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), carries the critical responsibility of ensuring equitable access to quality education.

As the country moves toward this long-term vision, the role of higher education institutions (HEIs) becomes significant. Universities not only shape the knowledge and skills of students but also cultivate their perspectives, expectations, and engagement in national development goals. The Palawan State University–Narra Campus (PSU–Narra), being one of the leading educational institutions in southern Palawan, is an important venue to understand how the youth perceive *AmBisyon Natin 2040*, what they expect from its realization, and how engaged they are in its attainment (Tomasella et al., 2023).

Students’ perceptions provide insights into how well they understand and accept the country’s development vision. Expectations reflect their outlook on the feasibility and potential impact of *AmBisyon Natin 2040* on their lives and communities. Meanwhile, engagement measures the extent of their participation in initiatives, programs, and activities aligned with the vision. Taken together, these dimensions are vital in determining the readiness and involvement of the younger generation in the pursuit of the country’s long-term aspirations.

Thus, this study aims to examine the perceptions, expectations, and engagement of PSU–Narra students toward the attainment of *AmBisyon Natin 2040*, highlighting the youth’s role as key partners in national development.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1. Age
- 1.2. Sex
- 1.3. Academic Year Level
- 1.4. Program Enrolled
2. What are the perceptions of PSU–Narra students toward AmBisyon Natin 2040?
3. What are the expectations of PSU–Narra students regarding the realization of AmBisyon Natin 2040?
4. What is the level of engagement of PSU–Narra students in activities aligned with AmBisyon Natin 2040?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profiles in terms of PSU-Narra students year level and program among perceptions, expectations, and engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative-descriptive correlational design. The descriptive component were used to determine the perceptions, expectations, and engagement of PSU–Narra students toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. Meanwhile, the correlational aspect will test whether significant relationships exist among variables. This design allows for systematic data collection, statistical description of trends, and analysis of relationships

Locale of the Study

The study conducted at Palawan State University – Narra Campus, located in the municipality of Narra, Palawan. The campus caters to students from various academic programs, including Political Science, Criminology, Education, and Agriculture etc.. As an academic institution in southern Palawan, PSU–Narra provides an ideal setting for exploring the youth’s perceptions and participation in long-term national development initiatives such as AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Population and Sampling

The population of the study consists of all 1,938 undergraduate students enrolled at PSU–Narra Campus during Academic Year 2025-2026.

The sample size of 332 were determined using Slovin’s Formula at a 5% margin of error:

A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from different programs and year levels. The computed sample will be proportionately distributed among the identified strata.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents were undergraduate students of PSU–Narra who meet the following inclusion criteria:

- Officially enrolled at PSU–Narra Campus during Academic Year 2025-2026.
- Willing to voluntarily participate in the study.

- Able to provide informed consent.

Research Instrument

The primary data-gathering tool will be a structured questionnaire, which will be divided into the following parts:

Part I: Respondents' demographic profile (age, sex, program, year level).

Part II: Perceptions of students toward AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Part III: Expectations of students regarding its realization.

Part IV: Engagement of students in activities aligned with Ambisyon Natin 2040.

Responses in Parts II, III, and IV will be measured using a 5-point Likert scale:

- 1 – Strongly Disagree
- 2 – Disagree
- 3 – Neutral
- 4 – Agree
- 5 – Strongly Agree

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools will be employed:

- **Frequency and Percentage Distribution** – to describe the demographic profile of respondents.
- **Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation** – to determine students' perceptions, expectations, and engagement levels.
- **Pearson's r Correlation Coefficient** – to examine the relationship among perceptions, expectations, and engagement of PSU-Narra Students.

Tables – were used to present descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages, for each variable of interest. These tables will provide a clear and organized summary of the data.

Results and Discussions

Table 2. Demographic Profiles of the Respondents

Sex	F	%
Female	142	43
Male	190	57
TOTAL	332	100%

In terms of sex, the majority were male (190 or 57%), while female respondents comprised 142 or 43% of the total. This indicates that male students were slightly more represented in the study, which may

reflect the enrollment distribution in the campus' male-dominated programs such as Bachelor of Science in Criminology and Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship.

Table 2.2 Age

Age	F	%
18-20	183	55
21-23	133	40
24-26	16	5
TOTAL	332	100%

For age, most respondents were between 18-23 years old, specifically 183 (55%) aged 18-20 and another 133 (40%) aged 21-23. Only 16 respondents (5%) were aged 24-26. This suggests that the participants mainly belong to the typical college-age group, which aligns with the study's focus on youth perceptions and engagement toward national development.

Table 2.3 Program Enrolled

Program Enrolled	F	%
Bachelor of Arts in Political Science	32	10
Bachelor of Elementary Education	36	11
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture	8	2
Bachelor of Science in Business Adm.-Marketing Management	32	10
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	32	10
Bachelor of Science in Computer Science	34	10
Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship	94	28
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	30	9
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	34	10
TOTAL	332	100%

Regarding program enrolment, the largest group came from Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship, followed by Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Science in Computer Science, Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management, and other programs such as Bachelor of Arts in Political Science, Bachelor of Science in Criminology, and Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management. The variation in the number of respondents per program is due to the use of stratified random sampling, in which the total sample was proportionally divided among programs to ensure balanced representation. This approach allowed each academic program to contribute meaningfully to the study, preventing overrepresentation from any single course.

Table 2.4 Academic Year Level

Year	F	%
1 st Year	85	25.6
2 nd Year	72	21.7
3 rd Year	87	26.2
4 th Year	88	26.5
TOTAL	332	100%

In terms of year level, respondents were fairly distributed. This even representation indicates that all academic levels were adequately included, allowing for comparison of responses across different stages of college life.

Table 3. Perceptions toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

Statement	Mean	Remarks
1. I am aware of AmBisyon Natin 2040 as the government's long-term vision for development.	3.35	Moderate Perception
2. AmBisyon Natin 2040 is relevant to the needs of the Filipino people.	3.86	Positive Perception
3. The vision of a "matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay" is achievable for all Filipinos.	3.65	Positive Perception
4. AmBisyon Natin 2040 provides a clear direction for the country's future.	3.79	Positive Perception
5. The goals of AmBisyon Natin 2040 align with me personal aspirations as a student.	3.85	Positive Perception
6. I believe AmBisyon Natin 2040 promotes inclusive growth and development.	3.56	Positive Perception
7. AmBisyon Natin 2040 strengthens national identity and unity among Filipinos.	3.60	Positive Perception
Grand Mean	3.67	Positive Perception

The findings in Table 3 shows that respondents generally agreed with those statements related to AmBisyon Natin 2040, obtaining a grand mean of 3.67 interpreted as Agree. This indicates that students have a positive perception that government's long-term vision and recognize its relevance to national development. Among the indicators, the statement "AmBisyon Natin 2040 is relevant to the needs of the Filipino people" have the highest mean of 3.86, implying that students acknowledge its importance in addressing that nations socio-economic needs. This shows that the respondents see AmBisyon Natin 2040 as a practical and people-centered framework for development. On the other hand, the statement "I am aware of AmBisyon Natin 2040 as the governments long-term vision for development" have the lowest mean of 3.35, which interpreted that they moderately agreed. This implies that while students have a positive view of the initiative, some still lack in-depth awareness or exposure to the details of the program.

The data reveal that PSU-Narra students perceived AmBisyon Natin 2040 positively, reflecting trust in its goals and alignment with personal aspirations. However, it remains a need for greater information dissemination to enhance awareness and understanding of the programs long-term impact.

Table 3.1. Awareness of AmBisyon Natin 2040 as the government's long-term vision for development.

Description	F	%
Strongly Unaware	23	6.93%
Unaware	52	15.66%
Neutral	92	27.71%
Aware	117	35.24%
Very Aware	48	14.46%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that the majority of respondents are aware of AmBisyon Natin 2040 as the government's long-term development vision. The highest percentage of responses falls under *Aware*, followed by *Very Aware*, indicating that many respondents recognize and acknowledge the program. Meanwhile, 27.71% of the respondents selected *Neutral*, and a smaller portion expressed unawareness. Combined, the *Aware* and *Very Aware* responses account nearly half of the total respondents, suggesting the information dissemination regarding AmBisyon Natin 2040 has been relatively effective. However, the relatively high percentage of *Neutral* responses implies that some respondents may lack sufficient knowledge or clear understanding of the program. The 22.59% who disagreed or strongly disagreed may reflected limited exposure or inadequate communication about the initiative. The findings indicate that respondents demonstrate a general level of awareness of AmBisyon Natin 2040. Nevertheless, the results also suggest the need for stronger information campaigns and public engagement to increase awareness and reduce neutral or negative perceptions.

Table 3.2. AmBisyon Natin 2040 is relevant to the needs of the Filipino people.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.51%
Disagree	54	16.27%
Neutral	40	12.05%
Agree	116	34.94%
Strongly Agree	117	35.24%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that most of the respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 is relevant to the needs of the Filipino people. A large portion of the respondents strongly agree (35.24%) and agree (34.94%) with the statement. Only a small percentage expressed strong disagreement, while some respondents remained neutral.

The combined percentage of respondents who agree and strongly agree (70.18%) indicates a generally positive perception of AmBisyon Natin 2040. This suggests that many respondents see the vision as aligned with the current and future needs of Filipinos. The relatively low percentage of disagreement implies limited resistance or negative perception toward the program. However, the presence of neutral responses may indicate that some respondents are either undecided or lack sufficient information about how the vision directly addresses public needs.

Table 3.3. The vision of a "matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay" is achievable for all Filipinos.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	26	7.83%
Disagree	51	15.36%
Neutral	54	16.27%

Agree	82	24.70%
Strongly Agree	119	35.84%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results show that a significant number of respondents believe that the vision of a “matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay” is achievable for all Filipinos. The highest percentage comes from those who strongly agree (35.84%), followed by those who agree. However, a noticeable portion of respondents either disagreed or remained neutral.

The findings suggest a generally optimistic outlook among respondents regarding the achievability of the national vision. More than half of the respondents agree or strongly agree (60.54%), indicating confidence in the government’s long-term goals. Nevertheless, the combined percentage of neutral and negative responses shows that some respondents may have doubts due to existing social and economic challenges. This implies the need for stronger implementation strategies and clearer communication to increase public confidence in achieving this vision.

Table 3.4. AmBisyon Natin 2040 provides a clear direction for the country’s future.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	11	3.31%
Disagree	44	13.25%
Neutral	66	19.88%
Agree	93	28.01%
Strongly Agree	118	35.54%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that most respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 provides a clear direction for the country’s future. The highest percentage of responses came from those who strongly agree (35.54%), followed by those who agree (28.01%). A smaller portion of respondents expressed disagreement, while some remained neutral.

The combined percentage of Agree and Strongly Agree responses (63.55%) indicates that a majority of respondents perceive AmBisyon Natin 2040 as a clear and guiding framework for national development. This suggests that the vision effectively communicates long-term goals for the country. However, the presence of neutral responses (19.88%) may indicate that some respondents are unsure or lack sufficient understanding of how the vision translates into concrete direction. This highlights the need for clearer communication and stronger public engagement regarding the long-term goals of the program.

Table 3.5. The goals of AmBisyon Natin 2040 align with me personal aspirations as a student.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	6	1.81%
Disagree	57	17.17%
Neutral	52	15.66%
Agree	84	25.30%
Strongly Agree	133	40.06%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results indicate that a large number of respondents believe that the goals of AmBisyon Natin 2040 align with their personal aspirations as students. The highest percentage of responses was recorded under Strongly Agree (40.06%), followed by Agree (25.30%). Only a small proportion of respondents strongly disagreed, while some expressed uncertainty.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (65.36%) suggest that many students see a strong connection between their personal goals and the objectives of AmBisyon Natin 2040. This implies that the national vision resonates with students' hopes for a better quality of life and future opportunities. However, the presence of neutral and disagreeing responses may reflect varying personal circumstances or limited awareness of how the national goals directly relate to individual aspirations. Strengthening student-centered discussions and awareness campaigns may help improve alignment and understanding.

Table 3.6. AmBisyon Natin 2040 promotes inclusive growth and development.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	29	8.73%
Disagree	40	12.05%
Neutral	65	19.58%
Agree	113	34.04%
Strongly Agree	85	25.60%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that most respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 promotes inclusive growth and development. A large proportion of the respondents agree (34.04%) and strongly agree (25.60%) with the statement. Meanwhile, some respondents remained neutral, while a smaller percentage expressed disagreement.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (59.64%) indicate that a majority of respondents perceive AmBisyon Natin 2040 as supportive of inclusive development. This suggests that

many believe the vision aims to benefit different sectors of society. However, the presence of neutral (19.58%) and disagreeing responses implies that some respondents may be uncertain or skeptical about whether inclusive growth is fully achieved in practice. This highlights the need for clearer implementation and communication of programs that ensure inclusivity across communities.

Table 3.7. AmBisyon Natin 2040 strengthens national identity and unity among Filipinos.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	11	3.31%
Disagree	66	19.88%
Neutral	57	17.17%
Agree	109	32.83%
Strongly Agree	89	26.81%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results indicate that many respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 helps strengthen national identity and unity among Filipinos. The highest percentage of responses falls under Agree (32.83%), followed by Strongly Agree (26.81%). However, a noticeable portion of respondents expressed disagreement or neutrality.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (59.64%) suggest that more than half of the respondents view AmBisyon Natin 2040 as contributing to national unity and shared identity. This implies that the vision resonates with respondents in terms of collective goals for the country. Nevertheless, the presence of neutral and disagreeing responses may reflect differences in personal experiences or perceptions of national cohesion. These findings suggest the importance of strengthening programs that promote shared values and a stronger sense of unity among Filipinos.

Table 4. Expectations regarding the Realization of AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Description/Statement	Mean	Remarks
1. The Philippine government has the capacity to realize AmBisyon Natin 2040.	3.09	Moderate Expectation
2. I expect improvements in education as part of AmBisyon Natin 2040.	3.20	Moderate Expectation
3. I expect job opportunities and decent work to increase through this vision.	3.31	Moderate Expectation
4. AmBisyon Natin 2040 will improve healthcare and social services for Filipinos.	3.66	High Expectation
5. I expect sustainable development and environmental protection to be achieved.	3.38	Moderate Expectation
6. I expect that poverty levels will significantly decrease by 2040.	3.24	Moderate Expectation

7. AmBisyon Natin 2040 will bring a better quality of life for my generation.	3.67	High Expectation
Total	3.36	Moderate Expectation

As presented in Table 4, the respondents obtained a grand mean of 3.36, interpreted as Moderately Agree. This indicates that PSU-Narra students holds moderate expectations toward that realization of AmBisyon Natin 2040. While they generally believe the vision could bring positive change, they remain curious about its full implementation. The statement “AmBisyon Natin 2040 will bring a better quality of life for my generation” gained the highest mean of 3.67, interpreted as Agree. This implies that students are optimistic that the long-term development plan will uplift living standards and provide greater opportunities for future generations. Similarly, expectations are high in areas related to healthcare and social services, suggesting confidence in government initiatives to improve citizen well-being. The indicator “The Philippine government has the capacity to realize AmBisyon Natin 2040” has the lowest mean which still falls under Moderately Agree and some respondents are uncertain about the government’s ability to sustain and fulfill the programs ambitious goals.

The results shows that students have hopeful yet realistic expectations towards AmBisyon Natin 2040. They recognize its potential benefits but also acknowledge that challenges the government may face in achieving its targets.

Table 4.1. The Philippine government has the capacity to realize AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	58	17.47%
Disagree	37	11.15%
Neutral	84	25.30%
Agree	124	37.35%
Strongly Agree	29	8.73%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows mixed perceptions regarding the capacity of the Philippine government to realize AmBisyon Natin 2040. The largest proportion of respondents agree (37.35%) that the government has the capacity to achieve the vision, while a notable percentage remains neutral. A considerable number of respondents also expressed disagreement.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (46.08%) suggest that less than half of the respondents have confidence in the government’s capacity to fully realize AmBisyon Natin 2040. This indicates moderate trust, but not strong confidence, among respondents. The relatively high percentage of neutral responses (25.30%) may reflect uncertainty or lack of sufficient information about government capabilities. Meanwhile, the presence of disagreeing responses suggests skepticism, possibly influenced by past experiences or concerns about governance and implementation challenges.

Table 4.2. Improvements in education as part of AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	53	15.96%
Disagree	55	16.57%
Neutral	46	13.86%
Agree	130	39.16%
Strongly Agree	48	14.46%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results indicate that many respondents expect improvements in education as part of AmBisyon Natin 2040. The highest percentage of responses falls under Agree (39.16%), followed by Strongly Agree (14.46%), suggesting positive expectations regarding the education sector.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (53.62%) show that more than half of the respondents are optimistic about educational improvements under AmBisyon Natin 2040. This reflects confidence in education as a priority area of the national vision. However, the presence of disagreeing and neutral responses indicates that some respondents may have concerns about the pace or effectiveness of educational reforms. These findings suggest the need for sustained policy efforts and visible improvements to strengthen public confidence in the education goals of AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Table 4.3. Job opportunities and decent work to increase through this vision.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	43	12.95%
Disagree	33	9.94%
Neutral	80	24.10%
Agree	129	38.86%
Strongly Agree	47	14.16%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that many respondents expect an increase in job opportunities and decent work through AmBisyon Natin 2040. The highest percentage of responses falls under Agree (38.86%), followed by Strongly Agree (14.16%). However, a considerable portion of respondents remained neutral, while some expressed disagreement.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (53.02%) indicate that more than half of the respondents are optimistic about improvements in employment opportunities under AmBisyon Natin 2040. This suggests confidence that the national vision can positively influence the labor market. Nevertheless, the relatively high percentage of neutral responses (24.10%) may reflect uncertainty about how the vision

will translate into actual job creation. The presence of disagreeing responses suggests that some respondents remain cautious, possibly due to current employment challenges or limited visibility of concrete outcomes.

Table 4.4. AmBisyon Natin 2040 will improve healthcare and social services for Filipinos.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	33	9.94%
Disagree	13	3.92%
Neutral	57	17.17%
Agree	160	48.19%
Strongly Agree	69	20.78%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results indicate that a majority of respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 will improve healthcare and social services. Almost half of the respondents agree (48.19%), while a significant portion strongly agree (20.78%), showing a generally positive expectation toward improvements in these sectors.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (68.97%) demonstrate strong optimism among respondents regarding healthcare and social service improvements under AmBisyon Natin 2040. This suggests that respondents view these sectors as key priorities of the national vision. The relatively low percentage of disagreement implies limited negative perception. However, the presence of neutral responses indicates that some respondents may still be uncertain about the extent or speed of improvements. Overall, the findings suggest positive public expectations but also highlight the importance of effective implementation to meet these expectations.

Table 4.5. Sustainable development and environmental protection to be achieved.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	21	6.33%
Disagree	84	25.30%
Neutral	28	8.43%
Agree	145	43.67%
Strongly Agree	54	16.27%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table indicates that a large portion of respondents expect sustainable development and environmental protection to be achieved under AmBisyon Natin 2040. The highest percentage of responses falls under Agree (43.67%), followed by Strongly Agree (16.27%), showing generally positive expectations toward environmental goals.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (59.94%) suggest that more than half of the respondents are optimistic about achieving sustainability and environmental protection. This reflects trust in the long-term vision's focus on environmental concerns. However, the relatively high percentage of Disagree responses (25.30%) indicates that some respondents remain doubtful, possibly due to ongoing environmental issues or perceived gaps in implementation. The findings suggest optimism tempered by realistic concerns.

Table 4.6. Poverty levels will significantly decrease by 2040.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	233	6.93%
Disagree	82	24.70%
Neutral	59	17.77%
Agree	127	38.25%
Strongly Agree	54	12.35%
TOTAL	332	100%

The results show that many respondents expect a significant decrease in poverty levels by 2040. The largest group of respondents agree (38.25%), followed by those who strongly agree (12.35%), indicating cautious optimism about poverty reduction under AmBisyon Natin 2040.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (50.60%) suggest that about half of the respondents believe poverty reduction is achievable by 2040. This reflects moderate confidence in the government's long-term strategies. However, the notable percentages of Disagree (24.70%) and Neutral (17.77%) responses indicate lingering doubts, likely influenced by persistent socio-economic challenges. These findings imply that while expectations are generally positive, stronger and more visible poverty-alleviation efforts are needed to build greater public confidence.

Table 4.7. AmBisyon Natin 2040 will bring a better quality of life for my generation.

Description	F	%
Strongly Disagree	5	1.51%
Disagree	38	11.45%
Neutral	78	23.49%
Agree	152	45.78%
Strongly Agree	59	17.77%
TOTAL	332	100%

The table shows that most respondents believe that AmBisyon Natin 2040 will bring a better quality of life for their generation. The highest percentage of responses falls under Agree (45.78%), followed by Strongly Agree (17.77%), indicating a generally positive outlook toward the long-term vision. Only a small portion of respondents expressed disagreement.

The combined Agree and Strongly Agree responses (63.55%) suggest that a clear majority of respondents are optimistic about the impact of AmBisyon Natin 2040 on their future quality of life. This indicates confidence in the government's long-term plans related to economic growth, social services, and overall well-being. Meanwhile, the Neutral responses (23.49%) may reflect uncertainty or limited awareness of how the vision will directly affect their lives. The very low percentage of Strongly Disagree (1.51%) implies minimal negative perception, suggesting that opposition to the program is relatively low among respondents.

Table 5. Engagement in Activities Aligned with AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Statement	Mean	Remarks
1. I participate in school or community activities that promote sustainable development.	3.55	Agree
2. I support programs and initiatives that promotes good governance and nation-building.	3.70	Agree
3. I am willing to take part in environmental conservation efforts.	3.68	Agree
4. I actively engage in discussions or campaigns about social and national issues.	3.37	Moderately Agree
5. I practice responsible citizenship, such as voting, volunteering, or advocacy.	3.57	Agree
6. I integrate the values of AmBisyon Natin 2040 (matatag, maginhawa, panatag) in my personal actions.	3.54	Agree
7. I encourage others to be aware and supportive of AmBisyon Natin 2040.	3.76	Agree
Grand Mean	3.67	Agree

As show in Table 5, the overall mean of 3.60 indicates that respondents Agree with the statements regarding their engagement in activities aligned with AmBisyon Natin 2040. This implies that students from PSU-Narra are actively involved and supportive of initiatives promoting sustainable development, good governance, and nation-building. The statement "I encourage others to be aware and supportive of AmBisyon Natin 2040" obtain the highest mean of 3.67, signifying that respondents not only value the vision but also influence others to engage with it. This reflects a sense of collective responsibility and advocacy among the students towards national development goals. On the other hand, "I actively engage in discussions or campaigns about social and national issues" received the lowest of 3.37 or Moderately Agree, suggesting that while students are generally supportive, not all are consistently participating in civic discussions or public campaigns.

The findings reveal that PSU-Narra students exhibit positive engagement behaviors that align with the principles of AmBisyon Natin 2040. Their willingness to participate in community efforts and promote awareness shows that young individuals recognize their role in achieving the long-term vision of a matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay for all Filipinos.

Table 6. Relationship between Year Level and PSU-Narra Students' Perceptions toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

	<i>Year Level</i>	
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Perceptions towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	-0.43333083	0.1657297

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of -0.43333083 indicates a weak negative correlation between the respondents' year level and their perceptions toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This means that as the students' year level increases, their level of perception toward the program tends to slightly decrease, although the relationship is very weak. Furthermore, the obtained p-value of 0.1657297 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, which implies that the relationship between year level and perceptions is not statistically significant.

This result shows that the students' perceptions of AmBisyon Natin 2040 do not differ significantly across different year levels. In other words, regardless of whether they are in lower or higher years, PSU-Narra students generally share similar levels of awareness and understanding of AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Table 7. Relationship between Year Level and PSU-Narra Students' Expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

	<i>Year Level</i>	
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Expectation towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	0.46440867	0.85310545

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of 0.46440867 indicates a moderate positive correlation between the respondents' year level and their expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This suggests that higher-year students tend to have slightly higher expectations compared to lower-year students. However, the obtained p-value of 0.85310545 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, meaning that this relationship is not statistically significant.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' year level and their expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This implies that students across different year levels share similar expectations regarding the government's long-term vision for national development.

Table 8. Relationship between Year Level and PSU-Narra Students' Engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

	<i>Year Level</i>	
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Engagement towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	-0.5947278	0.07949689

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of -0.5947278 indicates a moderate negative correlation between the respondents' year level and their engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This means that as the students' year level increases, their level of engagement in activities related to AmBisyon Natin 2040 tends to slightly decrease. However, the p-value of 0.07949689 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the correlation is not statistically significant.

This result implies that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' year level and their engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. In other words, the degree of students' participation in initiatives aligned with the national vision does not vary meaningfully across different year levels.

Table 9. Relationship between Program Enrolled and PSU-Narra Students' Perceptions toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

	<i>Program</i>	
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Perceptions towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	-0.1751918	0.32605241

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of -0.1751918 indicates a very weak negative correlation between the respondents' program and their perceptions toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This means that the type of academic program a student belongs to has little to no effect on how they perceive the goals and importance of AmBisyon Natin 2040. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.32605241 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, which implies that the relationship between the respondents' program and their perceptions is not statistically significant.

This result suggests that students from different programs share similar levels of perception toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. Their awareness and agreement with the vision's principles do not significantly vary across academic disciplines.

Table 10. Relationship between Program Enrolled and PSU-Narra Students' Expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

<i>Program</i>		
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Expectations towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	-0.21031625	0.29351383

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of -0.21031625 reveals a weak negative correlation between the respondents' program and their expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This means that the students' academic programs have minimal influence on how they anticipate or expect the outcomes of AmBisyon Natin 2040. Moreover, the p-value of 0.29351383, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicates that the relationship is not statistically significant.

This suggests that students from different programs generally hold similar expectations toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. Their optimism or outlook regarding the success of the national vision does not significantly differ across various academic disciplines.

Table 11. Relationship between Program Enrolled and PSU-Narra Students' Engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

<i>Program</i>		
	Pearson r-value	p-value
<i>PSU-Narra students Engagement towards AmBisyon Natin 2040</i>	-0.26658425	0.24403095

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$; Not significant if $p > 0.05$.

The computed Pearson r-value of -0.26658425 indicates a weak negative correlation between the respondents' program and their engagement toward AmBisyon Natin 2040. This suggests that students from various programs show only minimal variation in how they participate in or support activities related to the national vision. The p-value of 0.24403095, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, further confirms that the relationship is not statistically significant.

This means that students' engagement does not significantly depend on their academic program. Regardless of their course, PSU–Narra students demonstrate similar levels of involvement and participation toward achieving the goals of AmBisyon Natin 2040.

Based on these findings, the null hypothesis, which states that *there is no significant relationship among perceptions, expectations, and engagement of PSU–Narra students toward AmBisyon Natin 2040*, is accepted. Conversely, the alternative hypothesis is rejected. This implies that students' perceptions, expectations, and engagement toward *AmBisyon Natin 2040* are not significantly influenced by their year level or program, reflecting a generally uniform attitude and involvement among PSU–Narra students regardless of demographic differences.

Summary of Findings

This study entitled “Perceptions, Expectations, and Engagement of PSU-Narra Students Toward the Attainment of AmBisyon Natin 2040” aimed to assess how students of Palawan State University-Narra Campus understand, value, and participate in the realization of the governments long-term development vision. A quantitative-descriptive correlational design was used, involving 332 respondents selected through stratified random sampling. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, and Pearson's r .

The findings are summarized as follows:

1. Demographic Profiles
 - Sex: Majority of respondents were male
 - Age: Most were between 18-23 years old, representing the youth sector targeted by AmBisyon Natin 2040.
 - Program Enrolled: The largest group came from Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship, followed by other programs such as the Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Science in Criminology, and Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management.
 - Year Level: Respondents were evenly distributed across year levels, with the 3rd and 4th years slightly higher.
2. Perceptions Toward AmBisyon Natin 2040

Students agreed overall that AmBisyon Natin 2040 is relevant, achievable, and aligned with their aspirations. This shows generally positive perceptions but with room for greater awareness campaigns.
3. Expectations Regarding the Realization of AmBisyon Natin 2040

Students moderately agreed with statements reflecting optimism about AmBisyon Natin 2040's success. This shows that students are hopeful but cautious, aware of potential implementation challenges.
4. Engagement in Activities Aligned with AmBisyon Natin 2040

Students agreed overall that they engage in actions supporting the national vision, such as participating in sustainable development programs promoting awareness, and practicing responsible citizenship. This reflects active but varied engagement, showing youth willingness to contribute to national progress.
5. Relationships Among Perceptions, Expectations, and Engagement (Pearson's r)

Pearson correlation analysis showed no significant relationships between year level or program and students' perceptions, expectations, or engagement. While some weak or moderate correlations appeared, they were statistically insignificant. This indicates that

students' perception, expectation, and engagement levels are relatively independent of their demographic grouping.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Palawan State University-Narra students have positive perceptions of AmBisyon Natin 2040, recognizing its relevance and potential to uplift the nation's quality of life.
- Their expectations are moderately optimistic, showing no belief in the vision's goals but limited confidence in full government implementation.
- Students are actively engaged in civic and developmental activities, reflecting awareness of their role in nation-building.
- There is no significant correlation between perceptions, expectations, and engagement when analyzed by demographic variables, indicating consistent attitudes toward AmBisyon Natin 2040 across the student population.
- The null hypothesis (H_0), which states that there is no significant relationship among perceptions, expectations, and engagement of PSU-Narra students toward AmBisyon Natin 2040, is accepted. Conversely, the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected.

Recommendation

In light of the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

For Palawan State University-Narra:

- Integrate AmBisyon Natin 2040 and related Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in NSTP, GE, or major courses to deepen student awareness.
- Support student-led forums, contests, and extension programs promoting national development awareness.

For Student Organizations:

- Conduct outreach and advocacy projects that connect local community goals with the principles of matatag, maginhawa, at panatag na buhay.
- Encourage both male and female students to equally participate in national development-related activities to minimize engagement gaps by sex.

For Local Government Units (LGUs):

- Collaborate with universities in youth empowerment initiatives aligned with AmBisyon Natin 2040.
- Provide platforms for students to take part in local policy discussions and community development projects.

For Future Researchers:

- Include qualitative components (e.g., interviews or focus groups) to gain deeper insights into students' motivations and barriers to engagement.
- Expand the study to other campuses or provinces to compare results and identify regional differences.

REFERENCES

- Albert, J. R. G., Basillote, L. B., Alinsunurin, J. P., Vizmanos, J. F. V., Muñoz, M. S., & Hernandez, A. C. (2023). Sustainable development goal 4 on quality education for all: how does the Philippines fare and what needs to be done?.
- Al Qashouti, N., Yaqot, M., Franzoi, R. E., & Menezes, B. C. (2023). Educational system resilience during the Covid-19 pandemic - Review and perspective. *Education Sciences*, 13(9), Article 902.
- Ancho, I. (2021). Education policies and Covid-19 in the Philippines: Observations and inputs. *Interdisciplinary Research Review*, 16(4), 1
- Bastida, E. L., Tabia, F. G., Oliquino, C. S., Maurillo, M. C. A., Denzo, J. D. R., & Miel, J. S. (2024). Creating an SDG-Oriented Youth Engagement Plan: An Action Research. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, 24(3), 4.
- Bustos, R. (2024). Bridging the Gap: Aligning Higher Education Priorities with the Shifting Job Landscape in the Philippines. *Recoletos Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(1), 9-24.
- Cimene, F. T. A., Du, E. C., Alonsabe, O. C., Kurangking, J. A., Santander, M. E. D., Alvarez, J. B. G. C., ... & Uba (2023), M. L. NAVIGATING THE EDUCATIONAL LANDSCAPE: PHILOSOPHY, TRENDS, AND ISSUES IN THE PHILIPPINES.
- DepEd (Department of Education Philippines). 2024a. "K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum." Accessed on 15 May 2024. "Matatag Curriculum." Accessed on 18 May 2024.
- Faustino, N. (2022). The Life Force of Volunteerism in the Public Sector Towards an Enhanced Volunteer Program. *UNIVERSITAS-The Official Journal of University of Makati*, 10(2).
- Inocian, R. B., Dapat, L. C., Pacaña, G. B., & Lasala, G. M. (2019). Indigenizing and contextualizing the use of cooperative learning strategies. *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers and Teacher Education*, 9(2), 1-18.
- Lamberte, M. B., Manzano, G. N., Culaba, A. B., Mirabueno, J. B., & Tolentino, J. E. (2019). Proposed Research Agenda 2020-2025: Catching FIRE as the Global Economy Reshapes.
- Maneja, G. S., Galang, J. R. M., Cayanan, J. P., Roman, L. A. K. M., Tanguangco, A. L., Tolentino, A. C., & Tiria, G. C. Country's Research Priorities to the Research Initiative towards a Developed Research Agenda. *ASEAN Journal of Science and Engineering Education*, 3(1), 47-58.
- OFRENEO, R. E (2023). Social Protection for All Filipinos.
- Mendoza, J. B. (2025). A Review Using SWOT Analysis of Mendoza, Ofindo, and Poco's 2040 Reform Vision for Philippine Governance. *Journal of Exceptional Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1), 71-74.
- Operio, J. (2022). Philippine Local Government Leadership Styles, Business Relations, Influences and Issues in a New Normal Environment. In *Effective Public Administration Strategies for Global "New Normal"* (pp. 63-71). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Padilla, J., Casimiro, J. M., & Amigable, C. (2025). Assessing Senior High School Students' Awareness of Sustainable Development Goals in a Philippine STEM School. *Science Education International*, 36(1), 35-47.

- Reyes, C. M., Albert, J. R. G., Tabuga, A. D., Arboneda, A. A., Vizmanos, J. F. V., & Cabaero, C. C. (2019). *The Philippines' voluntary national review on the sustainable development goals* (No. 2019- 10). PIDS Discussion Paper Series.
- Tomasella, B., Wylie, A., & Gill, D. (2023). The role of higher education institutions (HEIs) in educating future leaders with social impact contributing to the sustainable development goals. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 19(4), 329-346.
- Tuaño, P. A. P., Sescon, J. T., Castillo, R. C. J. T., Lubangco, C. K., Ponce, B. J. H., & Vicario, P. M. M. H. (2025). Outlook and Policy Options for Philippine Employment Towards 2040. *Millennial Asia*, 09763996241313027.
- Velicaria-Luna, F. C., Estioco, M. C., Abante, M. V., & Vigonte, F. (2024). Upward or Wayward: A Glimpse into the Status of the Philippine Economic Policies and Strategies over the Past Decade. *Available at SSRN 4809413*.
- Villaruz, J. F. (2025). Speech by Dr. Joselito F. Villaruz during the state of the university address on January 28, 2025.